

Unpacking recovery talk: Applied linguistics and anorexia recovery narratives

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Narrative therapy has been widely used in the study of eating disorders (EDs), in line with a trend in therapeutical intervention (not limited to eating disorders) that has successfully probed patients' reports of their illness and recovery journeys in an attempt to better understand them and improve treatment outcomes. Recently, interest in recovery narratives has increased, not least because ED sufferers, and especially anorexia patients, often show ambivalence toward recovery—a factor that leads to high relapse rates. In light of this, investigating the linguistic features characterizing, respectively, the discourse of former anorexia sufferers who have successfully recovered, and of those who are still struggling, can help identify linguistic cues that may contribute to assessing patients' attitudes towards recovery. This paper examines the discursive construction of illness and recovery in anorexia stories from Reddit's r/AnorexiaRecovery, where recovering ED sufferers engage in conversation with their peers, often with the aim of finding support or solace (henceforth, 'struggling recovery posts'), and ED-focused medical websites featuring full recovery stories ('successful recovery narratives'). By analyzing recurrent lexical and syntactic features, this corpus-based study compares how ambivalence toward recovery is negotiated in successful versus struggling recovery discourse.

Keywords: Anorexia Recovery Discourse; Clinical Linguistics; Corpus-Based Clinical Research; Eating Disorders; Narrative Inquiry

1. Introduction

Eating disorders, including anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, and binge eating disorder, affect millions worldwide. A recent meta-analytical study (van Eeden et al., 2021) suggests that lifetime prevalence rates of anorexia nervosa might be up to 4% among females and 0.3% among males, though incidence figures vary quite substantially depending on the criteria adopted (cf. also Martínez-González et al., 2020), and other studies put the prevalence at a much higher rate (for instance Galmiche et al., 2019, put it in the range of 8%). While there appears to be some evidence that overall incidence rate has remained stable over the past decades, not all scholars agree, with some claiming a steady increase over the years. There seems to be general consensus, however, that

anorexia—historically considered a disorder affecting mainly young women in Western countries—has now spread globally, (Kokaze & Pike, 2024), and can be found across socioeconomic groups, cultures, genders, and sexual orientation (Calzo et al., 2017; Murray et al., 2017; Pike et al., 2014). There is also general agreement that onset age has decreased, with a growing number of young people (under 15 years of age) being diagnosed. Although such increase may be due to earlier detection (in turn driven by increased awareness), it is a cause of concern; rising evidence of links between social media use and poor body image and disordered eating (Frost & Rickwood, 2017; Holland & Tiggemann, 2016; Mingoia et al., 2017; Ryding & Kuss, 2020; Saiphoo & Vahedi, 2019; de Valle et al., 2021), compounded with the rise of social media use among children, add to this concern, making the argument for early intervention—long recognized as crucial (cf. Currin & Schmidt, 2005; le Grange & Loeb, 2007; Treasure & Russell, 2011; Hart et al., 2011)—even more pressing.

A further aspect of EDs in general, and anorexia nervosa in particular, is their typically chronic nature, with periods of recovery and relapse across the lifespan (Turner et al., 2015). Only 50% of affected individuals fully recover; anorexia has the highest mortality amongst all mental disorders (van Hoeken & Hoek, 2020). Treatment for anorexia nervosa has often proved elusive. Recently, narrative therapy has gained recognition as an effective approach by virtue of its presumed advantage over other treatment options to successfully help individuals reframe and reshape their relationship with food and their bodies (cf. Weber et al., 2006; Scott et al., 2013). As a therapeutic approach, it centers on the idea that people's identities are shaped by the stories they tell about themselves, a widespread assumption being that narrative therapy allows individuals to separate their identity from the disorder, viewing it as something external that they can challenge and transform. By externalizing the eating disorder, patients are encouraged to see it as a problem they can address, rather than an intrinsic part of who they are. This is argued to be potentially effective in reducing shame and fostering a sense of agency and empowerment, and though recent studies have shown an occasionally ambivalent attitude towards externalization on the part of patients (Voswinkel et al., 2021), it remains a key component of narrative therapy.

The importance of narrative in the treatment of anorexia has prompted an interest in the analysis of such narratives, primarily with a view to identifying in them cues that may signal patients' progress or relapse. More specifically, over the last few years a growing body of literature has emerged, focusing in particular on narratives of recovery (Chancellor et al., 2016; Conti, 2018; Shohet, 2007). While there is a widespread acknowledgement that full recovery is not easy to achieve in anorexia nervosa patients, and that narratives of 'successful' and 'struggling' recovery bear recognizable differences (see in

particular Shohet, 2007), most studies are qualitative in nature and offer limited evidence of linguistic patterns beyond the qualitative cases they are based on.

In this study, I aim to contribute to this growing field of inquiry by broadening the range of data analysed to include narratives of recovery—both successful and struggling—retrieved from online repositories, and investigating it using corpus linguistic techniques. In doing so, I draw on a burgeoning tradition of linguistic inquiry which has been making a growing contribution to healthcare practice. More specifically, as highlighted by Hunt and Harvey (2015, p. 151), the data-driven approach to language learning which characterizes corpus linguistics, with its emphasis on the analysis of authentic discourse, is a “natural match” for the ethos of evidence-based care in medicine (Harvey & Brown, 2012), which makes it particularly well suited to pedagogical interventions for healthcare providers. Extending the analysis to more diversified data, testing insights previously gained through purely qualitative studies, may help provide more robust evidence of the differences in the linguistic makeup of successful and struggling recovery stories, thus potentially contributing to a better understanding of anorexia recovery patterns.

2. Background

Anorexia nervosa is known for being particularly difficult to treat, not least (and possibly mainly) because of patients’ reluctance to accept and continue treatment. Studies of anorexia patients have detected “ambivalence about recovery and resistance to treatment” (Rance et al., 2017, p. 133; see also Cockell et al., 2003; Williams & Reid, 2010) accompanied by “high levels of awareness—about both their illness and themselves” (Rance et al., 2017, p. 133). As stressed by Rance et al. (2017), “irrespective of their position in the recovery process, all the women spoke both from a position of being caught up in their AN and from one of being at a distance from, and able to reflect on, it.” (p. 133).

Analysing anorexia patients’ discourse, Ronai (1994) talks about patients’ use of “narrative resistance,” a discursive behaviour that has been described by Rich (2006, p. 299) as “a way of resisting discursive constraint and constructing a positive ‘anorexic’ identity” which involves “rejecting the negative labels of pathology or irrationality and instead constructing a narrative of anorexia as affording them status, and empowerment.” As Rich underlines, for some of the (all female) patients participating in her study,

... the ending of anorexia would entail the loss of a particular subject position, and thus it was not unusual for them to engage in boundary

maintenance between those who were inside and those who were outside anorexia—or those who might ‘take it away’. (Rich, 2006, p. 299)

The quote above would appear to confirm the view that anorexia sufferers may benefit from therapeutic approaches “externalizing” the disorder so as to enable them to distinguish between their selves and their illness. A focus on the self—and on how one’s understanding of one’s self can be reconceptualized so as to enable life after anorexia—appears to be key to recovery, which, according to Shohet (2007, p. 346), may in fact “be understood as a psychological and interactionally discursive reframing of past, present, and imagined future selves, collaboratively authored by the self-starver and her clinicians and/or other relational partners.” While a common theme of narrativity is indeed “the ability to understand health and illness as transformation of identities and networks” (Arribas-Ayllon, 2021, p. 88), studies of anorexia recovery narratives suggest that such transformations often result from a discursive reframing which does not entail an abandonment, or a relinquishment, of a sufferer’s anorexic self. In a study by Conte, far from “giv[ing] up or eras[ing] their history” (Conte, 2018, p. 89), former sufferers saw it as “an identity position from which they authored and reauthored” a narrative of their self as both ill and recovered which they considered “acceptable” (Wetherell, 2005, p. 170) precisely because it did not erase any of their former identities. Conte suggests that such narratives may be read in terms of what Holland and Lave (2001, p. 3) call “history in person.” From this perspective, narrativity becomes a “gift” of sense-making after illness has disrupted the continuity of experience (Bruner, 2002): in the face of illness, events are translated into episodes (Somers, 1994, p. 616), with order being reassembled through a form of “emplotment” (Ricoeur, 1981) that turns such episodes into a story.

Within this overarching perspective, a small but significant number of studies has delved deeper into the linguistic make-up of anorexia recovery stories in an attempt to identify recurring discursive patterns which may help identify nodal points in the anorexia recovery process. Shohet (2007), whose research has already been mentioned, identifies four dimensions along which the small number of narratives of full and struggling recovery she analyzes differentiate, namely (1) epistemic certainty; (2) affiliation with clinical typifications and master narratives of the disorder; (3) continuity between past and present selves; and (4) linearity of temporal and causal progression of events (Shohet 2007). More specifically, compared to narratives of struggling recovery, narratives of full recovery display a higher level of epistemic certainty, greater affiliation with institutional narratives, a sharper break between the anorexic and the recovered self, and descriptions of recovery as a step-like progression complete with back- and fore-shadowing. By contrast, narratives of struggling recovery presented with less certainty, a high level of ambivalence towards

institutional narratives, porous boundaries between the anorexic and the recovered self, and an account of progression as cyclical, full of sideshadowing and hypotheticals (Shohet, 2007).

Identity positioning plays a key role also in the investigation of anorexia recovery online support groups carried out by Stommel (2009). In her study, Stommel highlights the importance of adopting what she calls the 'sick role' in order for sufferers to initiate a process of recovery. Using Conversation Analysis to study online interaction, she identifies recurrent patterns in participants' contributions; more specifically, she highlights novice users' deployment of interactive strategies aimed at minimizing vulnerability and displaying legitimacy, something which they do by using oral discourse features that express ambivalence, or an in-group/expert vocabulary that employs abbreviations and diagnoses. The latter are also crucial in demonstrating new entries' willingness to adopt the above-mentioned 'sick role', which is actively—and normatively—promoted by both participants and moderators as a necessary condition for starting the journey towards recovery.

Distinctive patterns of identity construction *vis-à-vis* anorexia were also identified by Hunt and Harvey's (2015) corpus-assisted analysis of pro-ana and of anorexia recovery. In their investigation of the lemmas *anorexic*, *anorexia*, and *ed/ED* (eating disorder) and their contexts of occurrence, they found that the adjective *anorexic* occurs more frequently in pro-ana websites, while in anorexia recovery discourse preference is given to the nouns *anorexia* and *ed/ED*, a use that appears to be both empowering in so far as it meets the need to separate sufferers from their illness, and disempowering in that it signals surrender to the authority of the therapist. Comparison with practitioners' reported patterns and the resulting finding triangulation show substantial alignment, thereby confirming the reliability of linguistic research for the purposes of significant patterns identification.

The above-mentioned findings offer valuable insights into anorexia sufferers' discourses and constitute the linguistic knowledge base on which the research presented in this article is built.

3. Method

3.1. Materials

In this article, I study anorexia recovery discourse as told by recovering and recovered anorexia patients. Following Shohet (2007), I distinguish between successful and struggling recovery discourse. The materials used for the analysis were collected from publicly available internet sources. Full recovery stories were retrieved from dedicated English-language websites, which were identified by putting the search string 'anorexia recovery stories' in the

popular search engine Google and manually sifting through the results to identify suitable sources. These were found in public repositories of stories, mostly curated by charities, featuring first-person accounts of recovery journeys authored by former sufferers. Such stories have been gaining increasing popularity over the last few years as awareness of the toll taken by eating disorders on individuals and their families has grown, and have been found to be successful not only in fostering hope among recovering anorexics, but also potentially reducing stigma (cf. Sheens et al., 2016). As for the struggling recovery stories, these were retrieved from the Reddit subgroup r/AnorexiaRecovery. Reddit—a popular internet-based platform that facilitates social interaction through the sharing of news stories, content ratings, and active discussion forums—has gained recognition as “an inexpensive source for high-quality data” (Jamnik & Lane, 2017) which can be particularly useful in psychological research and have indeed been used in prior studies of eating disorders (Nutley et al., 2021). The platform is structured into numerous communities, each focused on specific topics, known as subreddits, where registered users come together to discuss and exchange ideas related to their particular interests or—as in this case—concerns and conditions. These communities provide a rich environment for researchers to gather insights for their studies. In the case at hand, the Reddit subgroup from which materials were extracted can be described as functioning as a support group for recovering ED sufferers. Such support groups (not necessarily Reddit-based) are growing in popularity (Stommel, 2009) and testify to the rising importance of cyberspace as a “critical context for the construction of alternative identities and narratives relating to eating disorders” (Rich, 2006, p. 295).

Table 1
Corpus Composition

(Sub)corpus	Sources	Tokens	Type/token ratio
Successful recovery stories	Beat Eating Disorders (UK) (15 stories); OC87 Recovery Diaries (USA) (7 stories); Eating Disorders Victoria (AU) (10 stories); 32 stories in total	33,140	14.60
Struggling recovery posts	r/AnorexiaRecovery (215 posts)	35,380	11.77
TOTAL		68,520	

All materials were collected in April 2023; while the anorexia recovery stories cannot be dated with certainty, the Reddit posts covered the two-month period from February 1st to March 31st 2023. All materials are publicly available; for

the Reddit threads, usernames have been omitted to ensure user anonymity. The texts collected amount to just over 68,000 words, fairly equally split between full anorexia recovery stories and struggling recovery posts, as shown in Table 1 (above). Successful recovery stories vary in length, as do posts, the latter being, however, by and large more homogeneous. Only original posts were included in the corpus, comments being excluded because not relevant to the current study.

The two corpora comprise two very different sets of texts. Reddit posts are by their very nature short, focused on a single topic or issue, with limited narrative scope. Whether they can indeed qualify as 'narratives' is debatable, as they lack some of the hallmarks of narratives as they are commonly understood, i.e., in Ochs and Capp's (2001) words, as "coherent temporal progression[s] of events that may be reordered for rhetorical purposes and that is typically located in some past time and place" or as "plot line[s] that encompass a beginning, a middle, and an end, convey a particular perspective, and [are] designed for a particular audience who apprehend and shape its meaning" (p. 57). However, as Ochs and Capp point out,

Understanding narrative . . . compels going beyond these exemplars to probe less polished, less coherent narratives that pervade ordinary social encounters and are a hallmark of the human condition. These narratives have the character of rough works in progress, because interlocutors use narrative to grapple with unresolved life experiences . . . The plot line of these narratives may or may not encompass a beginning, middle, and end, given that the plot is what interlocutors are attempting to craft and that life events are not necessarily coherent nor immediately resolvable. (Ochs & Capp, 2001, p. 57)

This understanding of narrative may be argued to include both 'story statements', 'episodes' and complete narratives (Black & Bower, 1979). Some of the posts may indeed be understood as episodes resulting from the clustering of multiple story statements, qualifying as 'units of discourse analysis' (van Dijk, 1981); others may be closer to story statements not yet combined into episodes. By contrast, successful recovery stories are invariably narratives of the kind mentioned above: they have a beginning, a middle and an end, and typically some sort of moral teaching they are trying to convey. In a sense, however, they are the ultimate outcome of multiple tentative narratives, life events having been "not necessarily coherent nor immediately resolvable" prior to their successful reconstruction in story format. As this paper aims to identify the linguistic traits of these two different stages in anorexia recovery journeys, the different nature of the texts comprising the two subcorpora not only is not a disqualifying factor for comparative analysis,

but may indeed be a component of the narratives. Of course, Reddit posts cannot by their very nature coalesce into complete narratives, but it may well be that their event-focused or at most episodic configuration be one of the differential traits. This aspect is beyond the scope of this paper, but may be worth considering in future explorations.

3.2. Procedure

As mentioned above, the study aimed at identifying recurrent linguistic patterns in the two subcorpora, with a view to providing insights into the discursive features characterizing successful and struggling recovery stories respectively. To pursue this aim, classic corpus linguistic techniques (wordlists, keywords, wordsketches, concordances) were used in combination with discourse analysis against the background of the clinical narrative practices described above.

In combining (critical) discourse analysis with corpus linguistics, I am drawing on a well-established tradition (Baker, 2012; Baker et al., 2008; Gray & Biber, 2011; Mautner, 2009; Nartey & Mwinlaaru, 2019; Partington & Marchi, 2015) that has been yielding notable results for the best part of three decades now. The “useful methodological synergy” highlighted by Baker et al. (2008) has proven hugely influential, and especially so when applied to the investigation of issues that have societal impact.

Quantitative corpus analysis was conducted using the online software suite SketchEngine (Kilgariff et al., 2008; Kilgariff et al., 2014), which offers all the tools mentioned above and more. The research design is best described as corpus-driven, with salient discursive nodes being identified on the basis of statistical data, qualitatively investigated in their contexts of occurrence via discourse analytical approaches interpreting corpus data in the light of existing literature on anorexia and anorexia discourse.

As for the research design, a first step in the analysis was the extraction of frequency lists for each of the two subcorpora, with a view to identifying salient lexical items whose analysis in context may provide insights into the discursive construction of, respectively, struggling and successful recovery. Of particular importance were deemed to be differences in the collocational patterns of lexical items that occur in both corpora (for instance, *life*), as they may suggest different attitudes towards the same issue. At the same time, lexical features that appeared to be salient in one of the two subcorpora helped pinpoint elements of difference. To identify them, besides frequency lists, keywords (KWIC) were also extracted. These are words that, despite not necessarily being frequent in (one of) the two corpora in absolute terms, occur in said corpus with a significantly higher frequency than the other, thus indicating lexical items that are specific to one subcorpus compared to the other. This

helped identify corpus specificities, which were later investigated qualitatively through an in-depth analysis of the concordance lines in which they occurred.

4. Results

As mentioned above, as a first step in the investigation, frequency lists were extracted. This was done separately for different parts of speech. Owing to the similarity in size between the two corpora, raw frequencies are reported.

The first pair of frequency lists concerns nouns. Nouns are the first means we have to categorize reality, and as such they can be argued to embody in discourse those aspects of reality which are most relevant to its representation (see Table 1).

Table 1

Frequency List of Nouns in Struggling Versus Successful Recovery Discourse

Struggling RD	<i>f</i>	Successful RD	<i>f</i>
recovery	303	disorder	156
weight	234	time	150
food	163	recovery	135
day	136	life	127
time	128	weight	107
year	118	body	93
month	106	food	92
meal	104	thing	86
hunger	102	year	82
anorexia	96	people	79
body	89	Day	72
week	87	friend	64

While the two sets of nouns have considerable overlaps, with *recovery*, *weight*, *food*, *body*, *day*, *year* occurring in both subcorpora, the struggling recovery discourse corpus features *hunger* and *anorexia* among its most frequent nouns, while in the successful recovery discourse corpus appear *disorder*, but also *life*, *people* and *friend*, with the latter three nouns indicating an approach to life that includes a recovery of social relationships. This is confirmed by an overview of the passages in which the lemma occurs, some of which are reported below.

- (1) I am back at work full time and genuinely enjoy life, I have plans for the future! I can eat out with friends, go to events and places with people, I am living. (Successful recovery discourse)

- (2) Having anorexia, I was seen as a sick person, someone who was suffering and was never happy. Now I am seen as me, Riley: a happy, outgoing person. Someone who has gotten their life back and someone who is living life to the fullest. Life without anorexia brings so much happiness. I have rebuilt relationships with family and friends, started a new job, started a relationship and done so much more that I never thought would be possible. (Successful recovery discourse)

By contrast, occurrences of *life* in the struggling recovery corpus, besides being less frequent, are mostly embedded in negative statements, as shown in the following examples:

- (3) I've been in and out of general hospital and admitted to a children's EDU where I was sectioned and had the most traumatic experience of my life. (Struggling recovery discourse)
- (4) It's embarrassing to see myself this way and I hate every minute of my life. (Struggling recovery discourse)
- (5) I feel so trapped because the fear of gaining weight controls my entire life. (Struggling recovery discourse)

Time expressions (*time, day, week, month, year* in the struggling recovery discourse corpus, and *time, day, year* in the successful recovery discourse one) are frequent in both, suggesting that discourse is narratively organized, with the timeframe for struggling recovery narratives being broken down into smaller units, each of them being the object of specific focus. In both corpora, *time* typically occurs in the expression *the first time* (as confirmed by the high frequency of the adjective *first* in Tables 2); in struggling recovery stories, this refers for the most part to first times either posting, or having a specific experience associated with the recovery process, while in successful recovery stories it can refer to both illness and recovery experiences. In the successful recovery discourse corpus, time references are frequent but not as specific as in the struggling recovery posts. To those emerging from the frequency list, the adverb *now* must be added, which complements the other time expressions. The third most frequent adverb in successful recovery discourse with 63 occurrences, preceded only by *not* and *so*, *now* typically marks the difference between the recovered/recovering self and the sick self:

- (6) I still have bad days, but that is ok, I'm handling them a lot better now and using coping mechanisms that are not ED behaviours, which is a huge step. (Successful recovery discourse)

- (7) Over 5 years I would see people's posts on recovering or starting recovery, but for me that was always a dream far from my reach. Now after 6 years, I have made my dream into a reality. (Successful recovery discourse)
- (8) Exercise can be stress-relieving and not stress-inducing. I run in a proper pack now and I know people at Park Run because we wear the same T-shirts. My dog (and a village of other people) taught me to have fun with exercise. (Successful recovery discourse)

The lemma *weight*, whose appearance in the top ranks of both subcorpora is hardly surprising, given the type of discourse analyzed, lends itself to some interesting considerations. While an in-depth analysis of all its contexts of occurrence cannot be carried out because of space constraint, one pattern does stand out. In the struggling recovery discourse subcorpus, the expression *weight restored* occurs 20 times, compared to only 6 in the successful recovery discourse corpus. What is more, in the struggling discovery corpus *weight restored* appears as a clear identity label, as shown in the examples below:

- (9) Worried recovery is not safe for me i really truly want to recover fully. i'm weight restored atp and so incredibly unstable. i want full recovery very badly but keep getting extremely suicidal.
- (10) So, I am weight restored but still massively struggling with being rigid around food.
- (11) Background: Weight restored and have been meal plan compliant. I have been maintaining my weight. 6 months post discharge. I have been struggling to switch the plate by plate method from the exchange system.

The term—which is used as a classifier in the examples above (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004) identifies an anorexia sufferer whose weight is now in the normal range, though possibly still struggling with the eating disorder. Being *weight restored* appears to be associated with considerable anxiety, with sufferers mentioning multiple struggles associated with this stage in the recovery journey. The paucity of occurrences of *weight restored* in the successful recovery corpus, by contrast, would appear to indicate that the label is not as (or may no longer be) relevant once recovery has been achieved. The usage suggests the adoption, on the part of sufferers, of medical labels presumably introduced in the course of therapy, as suggested also, in example 11 above, by the expression *meal plan compliant*, which also would appear to be lifted wholesale from therapy talk or medical records. Frequency lists for adjectives, parts of which are reported in Tables 2, also provide interesting insights:

Table 2
Frequency List of Adjectives in Struggling Versus Successful Recovery Discourse

Struggling RD	<i>f</i>	Successful RD	<i>f</i>
extreme	64	eating	77
good	62	good	72
normal	58	first	40
hungry	51	sick	39
bad	45	hard	35
full	41	mental	32
first	40	same	28
healthy	39	able	26
hard	38	different	26

In the struggling recovery discourse corpus, *extreme* co-occurs regularly with *hunger*, which does indeed feature in the noun frequency list. The adjective/adverb *hard* occurs in both, highlighting the difficulties that beset the recovery journey, which fully recovered anorexia patients also recognize. *Good* also occurs in both, but *bad* is only present in the top position in struggling recovery discourse, where the adjective *healthy* also appears.

Healthy typically occurs with reference to *weight*, but its contexts of occurrence often suggest that being a healthy weight is not the hallmark of a success story. Quite the opposite—it typically occurs in passages where the dominant feeling is one of worry for perceived problems that persist despite the apparent improvement:

- (12) I've been trying to get through anorexia recovery, but all I can think about is food food food. I'm at the low end of a healthy bmi and was wondering when this will go away, as I literally can't focus on anything else. (Struggling recovery discourse)
- (13) Im not eating 100% freely so knowing that ill gain even MORE weight is difficult to hear. I don't want to eat anymore because Im at a "healthy" weight but i don't want to live with my eating disorder. (Struggling recovery discourse)
- (14) Has anorexia ruined by face? This sounds kinda weird but I've gotten back into a more healthy [*sic*] weight but my face is horrendously emaciated. Have I permanently ruined something? (Struggling recovery discourse)

The most noticeable difference between the two frequency lists, however, is the presence, in successful recovery discourse, of multiple references to *eating*

disorders (rarely referred to with the abbreviation ED), as well as the acknowledgement of having been *sick* and of having *mental* issues. These are remarkably absent from the top positions in the frequency lists of struggling recovery narratives, but are definitely salient in the successful recovery stories:

- (15) How many people are out there that were like me, starting to snowball and wanting it to stop, but getting overlooked because they weren't seen as sick enough yet to need help. (Successful recovery discourse)
- (16) I was convinced that nothing was wrong, and I just wanted a doctor to confirm that, however I walked out of that doctors appointment with referrals and a diagnosis of Anorexia Nervosa (AN) among other mental health conditions. I didn't accept my diagnosis, I didn't think anything was wrong because I didn't feel sick, I was convinced I was 'too big to be sick'. (Successful recovery discourse)
- (17) Despite the physical and emotional toll of my illness, I never believed that I was sick enough. Anorexia was the only eating disorder I grew up learning about, and unlike the "heroin-chic" imagery that was associated with it in the media, I wasn't dangerously skinny. (Successful recovery discourse)

The verb frequency lists also offered some interesting data. While the most frequent verbs in the two subcorpora by and large overlapped, some differences, however subtle, were detectable. Beside *be*, *have* and *do*, quite expectably the most frequent ones, there were similar rankings (but different frequencies, with struggling recovery discourse appearing to have a very high concentration of the same verbs) also for *feel* (329 vs 138 in struggling and successful recovery discourse respectively) and *eat* (415 vs 139). Both subcorpora also feature *know* in the top ranking positions (with 134 and 81 occurrences respectively for struggling and successful recovery discourse). *Recover* (109 occurrences) and *try* (107) are more salient in struggling recovery stories, whereas *start* (78) and *think* (77) emerged as more relatively frequent in successful recovery discourse.

Patterns associated with *know* in the two subcorpora are especially revealing. In struggling recovery discourse, the most frequent pattern is *I don't know* (33 occurrences), with several further occurrences of the verb appearing in questions, either direct or indirect (*does anyone know?* 5 occurrences; *how to know if*; *how do I know*; *I just wanted to know*). This is of course in line with the nature of the corpus, Reddit communities being loci where users post their questions. In the successful recovery stories, *know* occurs primarily in the past tense, with *I knew* appearing 26 times, while *I don't know* never occurs, and *I didn't know* occurs only twice. In the struggling recovery posts the *I don't know*

pattern is further compounded by 17 occurrences of the initialism *idk* (*I don't know*), which further emphasizes the uncertainty with which such discourse is imbued.

The verb *try*, rather salient in struggling recovery discourse, appears mostly in negative statements, indicating in the majority of cases frustrated attempts at either getting better or finding suitable help:

- (18) I've been trying so hard for so long but I'm just in a recovery limbo. (Struggling recovery discourse)
- (19) I'm trying hard to start following my MP. (Struggling recovery discourse)
- (20) I'm really trying recovery on my own this time and it's clearly not working, what can I do if my doctor isn't being of any help?? (Struggling recovery discourse)

As for verbs characterizing successful recovery discourse, the above-mentioned *start* appears, on the one hand, to indicate awareness of the onset of the disorder or of subsequent behavioral changes associated with it (see excerpts 21 and 22 below) and, on the other, to signal trust in recovery (excerpts 23 and 24):

- (21) Throughout years 7-8 I started eating less and less and, although I lost weight, it was never enough. (Successful recovery discourse)
- (22) I started browsing on Incognito Mode to learn how to lose weight faster. (Successful recovery discourse)
- (23) . . . I am starting to learn that I am OK as I am. (Successful recovery discourse)
- (24) I'm starting to try to accept my weight restored body. (Successful recovery discourse)

As the excerpts suggest, identifying the starting point of one's descent into anorexia is crucial to its recognition as an illness, which, as shown above, is another hallmark of successful recovery discourse. By the same token, former sufferers also display an awareness of when their journey to recovery started—again, establishing definite boundaries within which the illness has been finally constrained.

In addition to the above-mentioned patterns, identified on the basis of frequency data, further insights could be gleaned from the analysis of keywords—i.e., words which are significantly more frequent in one corpus compared to the other, despite not being highly frequent in absolute terms and therefore escaping detection in frequency lists. To identify keywords, the

frequency lists of two corpora are compared to each other, with each corpus being used as reference corpus for the other. The keywords identified for the successful recovery discourse corpus were *illness*, *deserve*, *trust* and *pretend*; those for the struggling recovery discourse corpus were *overshoot*, *freak*, *bloat* and *confuse*.

The two sets of keywords are striking in their indicating clearly defined attitudinal positions in the two subcorpora. In successful recovery discourse there is an acknowledgement of one's condition as an illness, and the recognition that one's sick behavior involved pretending; there is also a realization of one's value (*deserve*), and restored trust in oneself and one's social network:

- (25) It is an illness, much as it tries to convince us that it is an irremovable part of us.
- (26) I was recklessly approaching a precipice of thinness that few could attain, and, immersed in my illness, I viewed my size as an achievement.
- (27) I felt so much shame because, deep down, I wasn't the confident, talented girl that everyone thought me to be. I was a fraud. I had mastered the art of pretending, at pushing aside and locking away the insecurities I felt. I am strong in my recovery: imperfect, but resilient. I cling to my truth, above all else, that I deserve to nourish and love my whole self.
- (28) The recovery and discovery requires [*sic*] patience and confidence both from within and from those around you. The patience to discover the true nourishment you seek and the confidence to regain your Self. It requires trust in yourself once more and an acceptance of the encouragement from those who support you.

References to *illness* seem to be especially significant, especially in light of the need for sufferers to adopt a 'sick' role as a necessary step in their recovery journey. While *illness* occurs 31 times in the successful recovery discourse corpus, it is totally absent from the struggling recovery one. There are indeed some occurrences of *ill* (5) and *sick* (28), but the latter often has a more specific meaning, indicating vomiting as a consequence of overeating. When referring to anorexia (mentioned 91 times in the struggling recovery discourse corpus, and only 41 in the successful recovery discourse corpus), however, the struggling recovery discourse corpus features the use of the initialism ED. With 83 occurrences, this is just below the top 10 in the struggling recovery discourse corpus, while it only occurs 6 times in the successful recovery discourse corpus. As was the case with *weight restored*, ED appears to be part of a code shared by sufferers (cf. Hunt & Harvey, 2015) and possibly originating in therapeutic discourse, as inferable from the excerpts below:

- (29) after IP, i did OP for a couple of years which was very helpful. i can't afford either right now and the ED tries to convince me that i can't afford food at all. i know this isn't true and i know resources are available in my area if this were true.
- (30) don't really crave meat, but I haven't touched meat for years and I have no idea if I actually like it. Meat freaks me out, but I'm not sure if it's just my ed talking.
- (31) I challenged myself and bought some food which I don't know the calories of when I felt like it the past days. I couldn't enjoy all cause the ed thoughts are there but quieter.

In all these examples, ED is used in structures that externalize the illness, drawing a distinction between it and the sufferer.

Further characteristics of struggling recovery discourse which emerge from the keyword list are feelings of fear and confusion. *Overshoot*—a verb which is used to indicate that a recovering patient has gained more weight than planned—is a huge concern, while *bloating* (not necessarily related to overshooting) generates anxiety, a dominant feeling (as suggested by the salience of *freaking*) together with *confusion*:

- (32) Someone just asked why I've become fat. Please help me. Will the overshoot subside?
- (33) I have been told overshoot will go away but it really hasn't on me.
- (34) After eating a lot in extreme hunger, how do you deal with the bloating and the pain?
- (35) Today was my highest day at I'm freaking out.
- (36) It's not even 10am and I've consumed a days [*sic*] worth of food. Is there a point where I need to tell myself no?? I'm confused. Surely this is not healthy??

Caught in the dilemma of wanting to recover, and yet being reluctant to do so, sufferers voice their struggle, confirming the ambivalent attitude towards recovery often mentioned in the clinical literature on the topic.

5. Discussion

The data analyzed above confirm and reinforce some of the findings of recent literature on anorexia recovery discourse. On a purely qualitative level, and as already suggested when discussing corpus composition, it is to be pointed out that struggling recovery posts report on *events*: concise, occasionally to the

point of lacking internal cohesion, they can be considered as “authentic” (Ochs & Capps, 2001, p. 17) narratives qualifying as ‘history in the making’; by contrast, successful recovery stories are best understood as *episodes*—“coherent” narratives (Ochs & Capps, 2001, p. 17) within which history is reconstructed and identity re-authored. As Shohet (2007) highlights, following Ochs (2004),

. . . “coherent” narratives tend to be presented as an orderly, linear temporal and causal progression of events involving a beginning, middle, and end and a certain and constant moral stance, leading to a clear resolution of the problematic or unexpected event being recounted. By contrast, narratives that prioritize “authentic” experience often involve musing, inquiry, contradiction, dispute, and revision and present experience as an “enigmatic life episode” (Ochs, 2004, p. 269). (Shohet, 2007, pp. 347-348)

These different characteristics are clearly reflected in the lexical and rhetorical structuring of the two types of discourse investigated in this paper. Rhetorically, both discourses are organized around temporal frames, but while those used in struggling recovery discourse focus on specific instances (*the first time, this week* etc.), in successful recovery discourse the timeframe is broader, with verbs such as *start* identifying boundaries in a succession of steps or phases. The salience of the adverb *now*, which functions as a marker of distance from the past, confirms not only the existence of such temporal boundaries, but also an awareness of the demarcation between illness and recovery. In this respect, the use of the term *illness*, and the salience of the adjective *sick*, confirm that successful recovery goes through the adoption of the ‘sick role’ mentioned by Stommel (2009). The salience of the cognitive verb *know*, typically used in the past tense, also suggests a re-reading (or indeed re-authoring; Conti, 2018) of their identities. In the same direction goes also the use of the verb *pretend*, whereby former sufferers signal an awareness of their former, isolated self. This would appear to confirm Shohet’s (2007) claim that successful recovery discourse is characterized by epistemic certainty.

In struggling recovery discourse, confusion and ambivalence dominate. Not only is the word *confusion* a keyword, but expressions indicating uncertainty are salient. These include *I don’t know* and *idk*, but also interrogative structures such as *does anyone know?* The latter may be argued to be facilitated (or indeed prompted) by the discursive environment in which the discourse analyzed is embedded: after all, Reddit fora also act as support groups, where asking questions is the norm. However, it also supports Shohet’s (2007) finding that struggling recovery is characterized by uncertainty. In this corpus, moreover, ambiguity towards recovery (Rance et al., 2017) often emerges, with sufferers

voicing their concern about overshooting and at feeling bloated, with fear and anxiety coming through as dominant feelings.

Another characteristic of the struggling recovery discourse corpus is the frequent use of terminology and discursive patterns drawn from therapy talk. In particular, expressions such as *weight restored* and *overshooting* appear to belong to this shared language of anorexia therapy discourse (Stommel, 2009). The use of the initialism ED to refer to anorexia, and especially to distinguish between sufferers and their illness, is in line with this (as shown by Hunt & Harvey, 2015), and aligns with common therapeutic approaches (Sykes et al., 2022; Voswinkel et al., 2021): patients struggling with recovery adopt the lingo of therapy, but do not espouse its content to the full, maintaining an ambivalent attitude which fully recovered anorexic have overcome, together with the language associated with it—as if only complete recovery made it possible to distance themselves from the in-group discourse of anorexia sufferers.

6. Conclusion

In this article, I have endeavored to identify salient linguistic traits of struggling and successful anorexia recovery discourse. In doing so, I have relied on existing literature, both linguistic and carried out from within other disciplines. The analysis has confirmed the existence of such different discursive traits, corroborating findings from previous qualitative research. That this corpus-based study confirms such findings is significant, as it suggests that their validity may be extended beyond individual case studies.

Research such as the one presented in this article is eminently suited to being used in medical training. As Hunt and Harvey (2015) have convincingly argued, integrating linguistic analysis in anorexia research can have multiple benefits. Clinicians who are still in training could be made more aware of the language patients use when discussing their beliefs about weight and eating; by understanding the narratives patients share about their illness and the roles these serve both internally and in social interactions, professionals may be prompted to critically assess the discourses on weight and eating that they rely on; and large enough datasets may help healthcare professionals engage in practice-based research and derive conclusions that are supported by the empirical evidence contained within such data (Hunt & Harvey, 2015).

Clinical research has much to gain from engaging with applied linguistics; at the same time, applied linguists can learn much from clinicians' insights. Hopefully, closer collaborations will be forged in the future among researchers and professionals in these disciplines, thus jointly contributing to better understand, and possibly treat, an illness that claims too many lives.

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